

Applying Epidemiological Thinking to Assess Anti-Trafficking Interventions in the Thai Garment Industry

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Abstract

Despite decades of anti-trafficking interventions, there is a paucity of evidence-based research and informed strategies for strategic resource allocation. Research on human trafficking faces a multitude of methodological and data related challenges, threatening the success of achieving SDG Target 8.7 to end trafficking in all forms. Human trafficking is often described as having reached “epidemic” proportions by researchers and policymakers because of its scale and widespread adverse impact on individual and population health. If this is the case, then the science of studying epidemics may be well-suited to generate new research insights. Epidemiological modeling makes up the foundation of informed public health decision making. The same underlying mathematical and theoretical principles have been applied in the study of a wide range of social and behavioural phenomenon outside of a biomedical context. Here we propose that through appropriate adaption and contextualization, it may be possible to create a novel, human trafficking model to describe dynamics using the same approach as infectious disease modelling. We describe the intersection of epidemiology and human trafficking while proposing a conceptual framework to inform the development of a preliminary mathematical model. Our case study looks specifically at the garment industry in Thailand and we call for further engagement and collaboration with members of the data science and modeling communities to overcome gaps in fragmented and incomplete data. A rigorous modeling approach has potential to create a feedback loop between policymakers and practitioners leading to informed and enhanced anti-trafficking efforts.

Keywords – Human Trafficking; Epidemiology; Model Development; Garment Manufacturing

1 Introduction

Ending the widespread, complex human rights violation of human trafficking has been prioritized in the Sustainable Development Goals and 2030 Agenda, enshrined under SDG Target 8.7. Despite significant expenditure on counter-trafficking interventions and data collection, evidence-based empirical research and analytical evaluations of anti-trafficking programs are scarce (Cockbain et al., 2018). This paucity can be partly attributed to the compounding methodological and data-related challenges facing researchers, such as the hidden nature of trafficked individuals, gaps in data collection and sharing amongst stakeholders, and a lack of models which can account for the

various factors impacting trafficking dynamics (Aronowitz, 2010).

Actions to date taken to achieve Target 8.7 and monitor progress on the efforts to do so, have been generally assessed to be insufficient (Minderoo Foundation, 2019). This lack of progress has prompted researchers and practitioners to conceptualize and address human trafficking in novel ways, breaking away from the law-enforcement centric approach that has informed and dominated responses for the past few decades (Todres, 2011). Simultaneously, research interest is growing around how computational science, data science, operations research techniques and analytical methods can be applied in the fight against human trafficking (Konrad et al., 2017; Volodko et al., 2020). Harnessing data in new ways is necessary to drive progress forward and generate insights towards addressing this widespread form of exploitation. Translating the complex social and administrative data that are collected into actionable information and recommendations is crucial to informing future policies and evaluating current policies surrounding human trafficking (Fedorschak et al., 2014).

Forced labour and human trafficking are increasingly recognized as public health issues of global concern, thereby necessitating a public health response (Chisolm-Straker & Stoklosa, 2017). Epidemiology is a core function of public health that scientifically investigates disease causation to explain how diseases originate, spread and can be prevented. As a public health-human trafficking paradigm emerges, epidemiological methodologies are showing promise as a way to generate insights into trafficking activity and evaluate operational solutions (Fedina & DeForge, 2017). Human trafficking is frequently referred to as being an “epidemic” or having reached “epidemic proportions” by researchers, policymakers, and NGOs as a way of framing and contextualizing the problem. If such is the case, then the science of studying the dynamics of infectious disease (epidemiology) may be well suited to help advance knowledge of how to harness data and science to help achieve SDG Target 8.7.

2 Labour Trafficking Overview

The internationally accepted, encompassing definition of human trafficking is derived from the United Nations Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime

(UNODC, 2000), also known as the Palermo Protocol, which defines trafficking as:

“the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation”

Within this comprehensive definition, our research focuses specifically on trafficking for the purpose of labour exploitation. We understand labour exploitation to occur along a continuum, ranging from decent work and compliance with international labour standards at one end of the spectrum, to extreme forms of exploitation or forced labour at the opposite end (Skřivánková, 2010). Trafficking, then, is the series of exploitative acts that moves a worker towards forced labour through various criminal and labour law violations.

Historically, anti-trafficking initiatives and research have predominantly focused on, and overemphasized, sex trafficking and commercial sexual exploitation relative to other forms of human trafficking (Goździak & Vogel, 2020). However, as the scope of efforts has expanded over time to be more inclusive of labour trafficking, data has in fact shown a higher proportion of estimated victims of labour trafficking than sex trafficking (IOM, 2018). According to estimates from the International Labour Organization, there are upwards of 16 million people worldwide suffering from forced labour exploitation at any given time, compared to roughly 5 million victims of forced sexual exploitation (ILO, 2017). Given its massive scope and the fact that labour trafficking is broadly underrepresented in the literature, much more research and action in this domain is needed (Weitzer, 2014). Quantitative methodologies applied in the context of labour trafficking are particularly scarce, and the development of innovative ways to conceptualize and research trafficking are nascent (Bump & Goździak, 2008).

3 Utility and Relevance of Epidemiology to Trafficking Research

The idea of analyzing human trafficking through an epidemiological lens is not new (Rezaeian, 2016) and has been advocated as approach that could be useful to generate incidence studies (e.g., number of or rate at which new people are trafficked over a given time period); prevalence studies (e.g., number of people ever trafficked within a population, or over a specified period), and useful in sectoral or geographic contexts (Fedina & DeForge, 2017). Improving the precision of incidence and prevalence estimates has been identified as a top priority for the next generation of public health research on human trafficking (Rothman et al., 2017), and using epidemiological methodologies can help to “understand and track the prevalence, severity, trends and changes in human trafficking patterns and flows” (UNIAP, 2010). Moreover, epidemiologic processes such as population-level surveillance, risk factor exploration, and program evaluation

can aid policymakers and advocates to better combat trafficking (Todres, 2011). In addition to providing a holistic, systematic and analytical approach, public health’s focus on prevention and intervention—informed specifically by epidemiology—has been utilized in the study of other complex, interrelated social phenomena such as violence prevention and drug use (Compton et al., 2005; Dahlberg & Mercy, 2009).

Epidemiological thinking is well suited to assess complex trafficking dynamics and how to disrupt such dynamics as it considers the interconnected nature of causal and risk factors at the individual, community, and environmental levels (Gallo et al., in press). Applying an epidemiological framework to study organized crime networks has been suggested as a way to account for complexity and help design interventions and strategic policies rooted in sound scientific methodologies (Finnegan & Masys, 2020). As Akers and Lanier observe in their interdisciplinary application of epidemiology to the field of criminology, “epidemiological models, methods, and theories that consider disease patterns, distribution, and causal linkages are useful because human population modelling should not be limited to traditional interpretations of diseases from a biomedical framework” (2009, p. 400).

4 SEIR Model

Epidemiological modelling in its most foundational form begins by dividing a population of interest into a representative number of compartments based on individuals’ status with respect to the progression of the disease under study (Brauer et al., 2008). One of the simplest of these compartmental groupings is the SEIR model, which subdivides a population into susceptible, exposed, infectious, and recovered, respectively. Such models use sets of differential equations to determine the rate of change, per unit of time, between compartments. For example, in Figure 1, β represents how many individuals move from the susceptible stage to the infectious stage per unit of time (e.g. one year, one month, one week etc.). A wide range of derivations of this approach can be used (such as SIR, SIS, SEIS, etc.) depending on the dynamics of the disease in question and the specific types of questions a modeler is looking to answer.

Figure 1. SEIR Model and its components

Not only can an epidemiological model describe the dynamics of disease, it can also be prescriptive. Using epidemiological models, it is possible to simulate and analyze the impact of intervention and control strategies to predict and estimate how the size of populations within these compartments will change in response to interventions or variations in parameters.

Models like the SEIR helped to lay the original theoretical foundation for informed public health interventions and they have been used extensively in the study of and response to infectious diseases for over a century (Anderson, 1991).

¹ See (Martcheva, 2015) for further reading

Such simplified compartmental models have minimal computational requirements and can generally be used as a first attempt to characterize an emerging infectious disease outbreak (Brauer et al., 2008). As a starting point, it is a pragmatic way to make a preliminary attempt at understanding the disease dynamics, and can then later be further enriched to account for additional complexity and details in its formulation (Rodrigues, 2016).

Using epidemiological methodologies to investigate and model social problems is a nascent application of useful tools adapted from the field of public health with the overarching intention of reducing social inequalities and injustices (Koss, 2019). Compartmental, computational epidemiological models have seen a growing application outside of their long-standing traditional role associated with infectious disease. The simplest SIR model (susceptible, infectious, recovered) model and its derivatives such as the SEIR, have been used in a wide range of creative contexts to model a variety of social and behavioral phenomenon such as the spread of domestic violence (Sebil & Otoo, 2013), heroin addiction (Wangari & Stone, 2017), and burglary and violent crime (Ormerod, 2001). Using the same underlying mathematics and theoretical principles as classical infectious disease modeling, such studies investigate the impact of certain parameters and control mechanisms, and simulate different strategies to make predictions about their effects to ultimately understand how to reduce the incidence of the condition being analyzed. If we are to consider a social problem (in this case labour trafficking) as a “disease” then we must go further than simply presenting a conceptual analogy and further develop a quantitative approach.

5 Modelling Human Trafficking as an Epidemic

Mathematical modeling informs and supports decision-making for disease prevention, and can be an effective tool to support the projected efficacy of combinations of policy, program options and resource allocation for cost-effectiveness (Killewo et al., 2010). Indeed, researchers have modelled the spread of disease using dynamic epidemic models and successfully determined the potential impact of various disease intervention strategies, prioritized prevention needs and developed resource allocation plans (Aleman et al., 2011; Büyüktaktın et al., 2018). Such an approach is necessary in the anti-trafficking context given the variety of intervention options available that seek to reduce trafficking incidence, ranging from pre-trafficking awareness campaigns, to proactive victim identification through labour inspections, law enforcement interdiction, and post-trafficking health, social and reintegration services (Office on Drugs and Crime, 2008). Despite significant financial investment and the seriousness of the crime of human trafficking, many anti-human trafficking interventions continue to operate without an adequate evidence base or a systematic evaluation of how to allocate scarce resources (Davy, 2016).

Although extensive mental and physical health harms are caused by labour trafficking (Oram et al., 2012), the health and medical aspects of trafficking are secondary to our

principle objective of applying epidemiological methodologies. Instead of investigating adverse health impacts caused by, or associated with, trafficking, we use epidemiology as a tool to measure the extent and distribution of an *outcome* (Akers & Lanier, 2009), in this case, the outcome being an instance of trafficking or forced labour. Exploring such a preliminary approach has potential to make innovative use of existing data and can help to inform purposeful data collection for future research. This can eventually translate to providing useful information to policy makers and to help inform resource allocation for different intervention strategies.

6 Garment Manufacturing and Thailand Context

As we explore the idea of using epidemiological modelling to study trafficking, we need to refine our approach to a geographical and sectoral focus where there is both broader interest and relevance to stakeholders in better understanding patterns and investigating the dynamics of trafficking. Globally, the apparel manufacturing industry is ranked second highest in terms of risk of trafficking and forced labour as employers seek to keep production costs low through coercive tactics that include illegal wage deductions, withholding of identity documents, and restrictions on movements (Walk Free Foundation, 2018). Forced labour in the manufacturing sector represents 15% of all trafficking victims globally and the Asia Pacific region has the highest absolute number victims, accounting for an estimated 64% of cases worldwide (ILO, 2017). The apparel manufacturing industry is one of the largest employers of migrant workers in Thailand and nearly 80% of all migrants in Thailand are from Myanmar (MAP Foundation, 2014). The domestic labour force of Thailand is projected to shrink by 2022 and the demand for low-skilled migrants workers who are most vulnerable to trafficking will continue to rise (International Labour Organization & Asian Development Bank, 2014).

Mae Sot is a city in the Tak Province of Thailand located along one of the most porous parts of the Thai-Myanmar border. Mae Sot is a Special Border Economic Zone, giving it preferential status for attracting investment, which has led it to become a hub of garment and textile manufacturing that relies on a workforce of almost exclusively migrant laborers coming from neighboring Burma (MAP Foundation, 2014). Recent high profile investigations have linked abuses in garment factories in Mae Sot to supply chains of global brands such as Starbucks and Bauer Hockey (Bangkok Post, 2019). Extensive reports of child labour, forced labour and human trafficking over the past two decades have emerged from Mae Sot, attributed to an environment with unscrupulous employers and recruiters, lack of enforcement of labour protections, and a steady influx of vulnerable individuals willing to work under exploitative conditions (ILO, 2006; Meyer et al., 2015). Mae Sot was selected as our focus for this case study because labour trafficking in this region is well-studied and documented, providing an availability of data from multiple sources that can provide a more holistic picture of the many factors influencing trafficking. This includes information on migration flows, border-crossings, exposure to anti-trafficking awareness

programs, NGO services, labour inspections, workforce composition, problems at the workplace and more. Data was sourced from various NGO, IGO and official governmental reports and databases including the International Labour Organization, the International Organization for Migration, the Thai Ministry of Labour, Ministry of Education, the Global Slavery Index, and the Migrants Assistance Program Foundation as a starting point to inform our hypothetical model.

7 Model Development

We follow an analytical approach to model development (Nganwa et al., 2010) consisting of six major steps: a) developing a knowledge base b) developing a conceptual model c) developing a mathematical model d) developing a simulation model e) testing, validating, performing sensitivity analysis and updating the model and f) implementing the model. The broader objective would be to follow such an iterative process to eventually lead to the implementation of an operationalized model, one which can provide a feedback loop of useful and actionable information between practitioners and policymakers.

7.1 Developing a Knowledge Base

We begin by analyzing the problem of trafficking through an epidemiological lens. An epidemiologic problem oriented approach (EPOA) provides a scientific framework for the collection, organization, and analysis of epidemiological information which facilitates the development of systematic and structured knowledge bases (Nganwa et al., 2010). Developing such a structure is pertinent to the enhanced comprehension of labour trafficking dynamics by predicting the susceptibility of a person to trafficking, understanding the relationship between victims and traffickers, and evaluating the impact of responses (Gallo et al., in press).

Figure 2: Epidemiological triad comparing Zika virus (orange) to labor trafficking (green)

The EPOA methodology has been used in the study of infectious diseases such as HIV/AIDS (Tameru et al., 2012) and African trypanosomiasis (Habtemariam, 1989) to develop models for computational epidemiologic case studies (Nganwa et al., 2010) and to better describe disease transmission dynamics (Dibaba & Daborn, 2019). The core components of infectious disease transmission are

traditionally organized into host, environment, agent, and vector. Measures for control and prevention require an assessment of each of these and their interaction with one another. To develop our analogous representation of labour trafficking as a “disease”, we have explored the EPOA in depth (Gallo et al., in press) and direct the reader to that paper for a more detailed understanding. Figure 2 provides a succinct description of our analogies between conventional epidemiological terms (in this case, Zika virus, in orange) and labor trafficking activity (in green). Organizing the constituent elements that are necessary to understand an epidemiological approach helps us to look for overlaps and the intersection of human trafficking and epidemiology.

7.2 Developing a Conceptual Model

To adapt a compartmental approach to represent labour trafficking, we require a basis informed by domain specific research to subdivide a population (i.e. how do we most accurately represent *susceptible*, *infected*, etc. based on practical considerations of how trafficking occurs in reality in the Mae Sot region). Given that labour trafficking does not occur through the transmission of an infectious pathogen there will be no truly direct equivalent measure, however for the purpose of modeling we sought to find a theoretical parallel that can serve as an adequate proxy measure.

Zimmerman et al. (2011) describe a conceptual model that organizes the different “Stages of the Human Trafficking Process” into a eponymous framework of cumulative risk that occurs across time and geography. The four main stages of the human trafficking process are; **recruitment, travel & transit, exploitation, and integration / reintegration**. In developing our conceptual framework for a dynamic human trafficking model, we adapt this compartmental approach and map these four stages onto **susceptible, exposed, infected and recovered** (SEIR).

Fig.3 An SEIR model mapped to the four stages of the human trafficking process

Zimmerman et al.’s (2011) analysis is framed from a health and human trafficking lens, and each different stage represents an opportunity for intervention and risk mitigation (Figure 3). Drawing on theories of population mobility, health and factors associated with exploitation, Zimmerman et al.’s (2011) conceptual model was designed to inform policy, intervention and research, making it very suitable for our proposed application to the four-stage SEIR model.

The **recruitment** stage, which we map onto the *susceptible* stage is the first in the multi-stage trafficking process when individuals are susceptible to exploitative and deceitful practices that lure them into a situation that can exacerbate pre-existing vulnerabilities. Recruitment agencies that facilitate economic migration for prospective migrants oftentimes control every aspect the process, leading to

conditions where exploitative practices are enabled and thrive (ILO, 2020).

Next is the **travel-transit** stage, mapped onto the *exposed*, where an individual departs with a trafficker and travels to their destination, oftentimes involving immigration violations, dangerous and/or multiple forms of transportation, high-risk border crossings, or forged documents (David et al., 2019). This stage is where an individual is first exposed to more serious forms of harm with more than half of victims of human trafficking worldwide reported being exposed to violence or coercion en route to their destination (IOM, 2018).

The **exploitation** stage is the period of time in which the abuses occur that are most commonly associated with human trafficking such as physical and psychological coercion, deprivation and confinement, and excessive working hours under threat of punishment (Zimmerman et al., 2011). To continue the analogous references to disease, this is when an individual is “*infected*” or experiencing the most severe symptoms associated with the condition.

Lastly, the **integration/reintegration** stage is when an individual is no longer in exploitative circumstances and becomes an active member of the economic, cultural, civic and political life in either the country where they were exploited or in their home country if they return. This stage is mapped onto the *recovered* compartment, although it does not imply recovery in an absolute sense as victims are frequently subject to re-trafficking.

7.3 Development of a Mathematical Model (Next Steps)

Now that we have identified the geographical/sectoral area of focus and developed our conceptual approach, the next step is to explore the possibility of a preliminary mathematical model to describe labour trafficking in the garment manufacturing sector of Mae Sot. As labour trafficking is an incredibly complex social and economic phenomenon, it is important to note that our compartmentalized approach would never be perfectly representative of how labour trafficking occurs in reality where the lines are often blurred between each of those stages of trafficking. However, as with all modeling of any complex system, we seek to strike a balance between representativeness, data availability, and the level of detail needed to generate useful and insightful model outputs. Striking that balance will involve consultation with data science and modeling experts for refinement and identification of the gaps in the existing secondary data we have collected.

Due to the many challenges associated with collecting information on human trafficking as described above, it is very likely that such data will be unable to fit properly into a more detailed epidemiological model or immediately give any useful model outputs. As no primary data collection was done in this research thus far, we rely entirely on publicly available secondary data from disparate sources and time points. Data science offers ways to augment incomplete data, and further exploration of the data landscape and which methods could potentially address these gaps is

necessary for refinement. We call on the data science community to help identify methods which can make use of existing data and best methods for future data collection which can be used for epidemiological modeling, which in turn can be used to deliver insights to policy makers. In addition to examining new ways forward, we also plan to engage in stakeholder consultation to analyze the feasibility of such an approach as it pertains to future data collection and other considerations of potential implementation.

8 Conclusion

Transmission-dynamic infectious disease models like the SEIR have been used in a variety of creative ways to analyze social and behavioural phenomenon outside of a biomedical context. Labour trafficking is a global public health concern, making epidemiology particularly relevant in studying and addressing it. Epidemiology offers powerful tools that, if appropriately adapted to fit the context of labour trafficking, can shed light on observed dynamics and make predictions about the effectiveness of control measures. Bridging the gaps between SDG-related data generated by governments, NGOs, and other organizations requires the scientific community to investigate novel quantitative approaches that can deliver insights for policymakers. The burgeoning research interest at the intersection of human trafficking and public health holds potential to generate useful conceptual frameworks, inform evaluation activities, and support predictive modelling. The cross-fertilization of methods from computational epidemiology and anti-trafficking expertise presents opportunities to make predictions regarding the effectiveness of interventions, simulate the impact of policy changes and resource allocation, and gain new insights into the dynamics of human trafficking. We are in the model development process of creating a dynamic representation of human trafficking systems, adapting a well-known and validated methodology for modeling from the field of public health. Such interdisciplinary approaches are necessary to address SDG Target 8.7 and we hope to spark further discussion and collaboration that leads to innovative uses of data and science.

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